

SONIC FOOTPRINTS OF WEB TRACKING

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ABSTRACT

Web tracking is found on 90 % of common websites. It facilitates online behavior analysis which can reveal insights into sensitive personal data of an individual. Most users are not aware of the amount of web tracking happening in the background. We present an interactive demonstration of web tracker sonification which is designed to promote awareness for online privacy issues by disclosing the amount of web tracking through sound. While the user is browsing the web, data exchanged with web tracking hosts is transformed into sonic events.

In the demonstration, users can try out different websites testing several browsers, with and without ad blocking additions, and compare the different sonic experiences. Additionally, we provide a Wi-Fi access point to which users can connect with their mobile devices so they can listen to the data transferred to third-party tracking providers from their own devices. This demonstration aims to spark discussion not only regarding the sonification design, but to widen the discourse into a critical reflection of online privacy and surveillance issues.

1. INTRODUCTION

Web tracking is the collection of information about a particular user's activity on the World Wide Web. Web tracking technologies are found in 90 % of common websites and in 60 % of websites with highly privacy-critical content [1]. A person's browsing behavior can reveal insights into his or her personality, habits and sensitive aspects such as financial and medical situation or political views. Hence, web tracking may constitute a serious privacy threat [2]. Although complex and very diverse, the ecosystem of web trackers is dominated by a small number of companies, notably by Google and Facebook, who are inconspicuously present as third-party data collectors on many websites [3]. The average user has no sufficient awareness of the extent and possibilities of web tracking [4].

We use sonification of hidden web tracking as a means of raising awareness, creating interest and stimulating reflection on web tracking and privacy issues. The data exchanged with web tracking providers is transformed to di-

rect auditory feedback while browsing. Using sound for disclosing the tracking activity allows the user to reflect on web tracking and privacy issues without having to interrupt the interaction on the web in the visual modality.

2. CONCEPT AND FRAMEWORK

Our framework for live web tracking analysis monitors network traffic, filters connections to known web trackers, extracts tracking-related events, and sends these to a sound generator via OSC¹ (Figure 1). The software runs in the background while the user is browsing the web.

Figure 1. System overview

The framework is implemented in Python. We monitor network traffic with several TShark² processes. These processes listen to traffic on the selected network connection on ports 80 (HTTP) and 443 (HTTPS). They are configured with filter lists of web tracker IP addresses, so only traffic to these hosts is analyzed. Two types of events are extracted: Initial connection to a tracking host (SYN) and data exchange with that host (GET and TLS Application Data). Data exchange is sonified by short bleeps consisting of a layered sound (low mallets and high shaped noise). Each tracker IP address is mapped to a certain note. If data is exchanged with the same IP again, this results in the same sound. Although, due to the vast amount of trackers, several IPs are mapped to the same note. An exemplary video is hosted on YouTube³.

To raise awareness for the prevalence of the top 10 most widespread tracking companies, an audio recording of the company's name is played in a whispered manner each time an initial connection is made to the respective host. Some of the companies are well known to users, others are not (e.g., ComScore). The whispered names are supposed to stimulate questions about these companies as well.

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¹ Open Sound Control: <http://opensoundcontrol.org>

² text-based version of wireshark: <https://www.wireshark.org>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ug3GjEe801k>

Further details on our framework for web tracker sonification are given in our ICAD 2019 paper [5]. Compared to the framework presented there, key enhancements of the system used for this demonstration include optimized country-specific filter lists, choice of the sound generator (open source Sonic Pi [6] in place of Ableton Live) and the ability to demonstrate the system not only with a local browser, but to test it with any Wi-Fi enabled device, e.g., laptops or smartphones. We open a secondary Wi-Fi network where our computer acts as an access point. Users can connect to this network with their own device and acoustically explore the data transfer from these devices to web tracking hosts. The sounds are generated on the host computer. In addition to monitoring tracking on websites, this enables listening to exchanges of data between other applications (e.g., mobile games) and web tracking companies as well.

3. DEMONSTRATION

We present two interactive demonstrations of our web tracker sonification. In the first demonstration, users can explore websites of their choice with two browsers (Mozilla Firefox with activated ad blocking plug-ins and native Google Chrome). This aims to raise awareness of web tracking and data-driven economies. Allegedly "free" websites and online services are often connected to a variety of web trackers as part of their business model.

For the second demonstration, we open a secondary Wi-Fi network which users can connect their own personal devices to. This facilitates sonification of traffic to web trackers from user devices and comparison of applications in terms of privacy. The audience can explore the sonic variations between different smartphones and apps. By using their own devices, there is a personal connection to the tracking events and to the data exchanged. This is aimed to spark discussions about tracking, privacy and surveillance on a personal level.

4. RELATED WORK

Sonification of network traffic monitoring to achieve higher situational awareness has been researched widely (see the overview in [7]). The scope of our approach, however, focuses on the average user who, in contrast to network operations professionals, is often unaware of the extent of web tracking [4]. Here, the term "awareness" refers to a general consciousness of the prevalence of web tracking.

Soundbeam by Hutchins et al. [8] is a related project. It sonifies third-party connections extracted by Mozilla Lightbeam, a plug-in for the Mozilla Firefox browser. Our approach of monitoring the internet traffic itself instead of using a browser plug-in extends the potential by supporting all browsers and applications, different web tracker lists, and the capability to monitor traffic of any device connected to a Wi-Fi spawned by the host computer.

Listening Back by Guffond [9] aims to raise awareness for online surveillance and privacy issues. It is a plug-in for the Chrome browser that sonifies access to browser cookies

in real time during browsing and aims to be a "mediator of the invisible", analogous to our approach.

5. CONCLUSION

We demonstrate two applications of our web tracker sonification: First, trying out different websites, browsers and ad blocking add-ons and second, providing a Wi-Fi network that visitors can connect to with their mobile devices to experience the data transferred to tracking providers by their own devices and applications. This provides tangible access to the relationship between usage of online services and tracking data collection. The demonstration is aimed to spark discussion in three domains: regarding the technical implementation of the framework, the sonification and sound design choices, and addressing online tracking, surveillance and privacy issues in a broader scope.

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